

Random Vibration Fatigue Analysis of a Multi-material Battery Pack Structure

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Introduction

- Electric motors are appealing as power source for eco-friendly automobiles
- Weight reduction for fuel efficiency → possibly in battery pack component
 - Increasing usage of fiber-reinforced plastic (FRP) due to high specific stiffness
- Concern: steady random vibration loading during drive
 - Fatigue life of the structure must be considered
 - Possible reduction in design costs by using numerical method
- In this research,

Numerical fatigue analysis of a multi-material battery pack through a typical mode-based approach

Ex. Hyundai KONA

Electric powertrain

Battery pack system

Fatigue life prediction

Composite material

- The multi-material battery pack consists of metal frames and composite casings
- Proposed composite structure
 - Laminate structure: $[LFT_1/WFT_3/LFT_1]_T$ (0.7 mm thickness)
 - LFT : Long Fiber Thermoplastic (discontinuous glass fiber/Polypropylene)
 - WFT : Woven Fiber Thermoplastic (2/2 twill woven glass fiber/Polypropylene)

Flowchart of the analysis _{1/2}

Evaluation stage

Obtain vibration properties of the structure

(1) FE modelling (p.6)

Numerical model of multi-material battery pack

Geometry, mesh, ...

Composite
Batteries
Aluminum
Composite

(2) Frequency analysis (p.7)

Extract natural modes and natural frequencies

(3) Harmonic response analysis (p.8)

Response functions **over freq.** (amplitude & phase lag) expressing harmonic response

for each natural mode
for each node
for each stress component

Flowchart of the analysis _{2/2}

Fatigue analysis stage Apply random vibration loading to the structure

(4) Loading and response (p.9)

Vibration loading defined over freq.

Response functions

Amplitude distribution over freq.

(5) Vibration counting (p.10)

Dirlik's method

Amplitude-frequency relation

Probability-amplitude relation

(6) Life prediction (p.11)

Linear damage accumulation

Fatigue life prediction

- **Multi-material structure**
 - **Composite** : Cover, Carrier
 - **Aluminum** : Frames, Plate
 - **Rigid body** : Batteries
- **Composite**: [LFT₁/WFT₃/LFT₁]_T (0.7 mm)
- ***TIE constraints between connected parts**
 - No relative motion between two surfaces
- **Elements of parts:**

Parts	Material	Element type	Number of elements
Cover	Composite	Shell (S4R)	61034
Carrier		Continuum shell (SC8R)	33841
Frame	Aluminum	Internal	54742
		External	166052
Plate			179403
Batteries	Rigid body	Rigid solid (R3D4)	4496×8

- Extraction of natural modes and natural frequencies

M^{MN} : mass matrix F^N : load at the tip α : mode number
 C^{MN} : damping matrix u^M : displacement of the tip ω_α : natural frequency
 K^{MN} : stiffness matrix M, N : degrees of freedom ϕ_α : mode shape

- These natural modes are
 - Harmonic oscillation
 - Harmonic loading (input) → Harmonic motion (response)
 - Linear combination of modes → Any vibration shape

→ Harmonic response analysis for relation between input and response

- Frequency response function (FRF), H_α (complex function)

$$H_\alpha = \frac{A_{\text{resp}}}{A_{\text{input}}} e^{i\theta}$$

$$q_\alpha(f) = H_\alpha(f) f_\alpha(f)$$

Response Input

A_{input} : amplitude of **input loading** θ : phase lag
 A_{resp} : amplitude of **response motion** α : mode number

$f_\alpha = f_{0\alpha} e^{2\pi i f t}$: input loading
 q_α : generalized displacement f : frequency

- Obtaining stress values

Relation with global FRF

$$\sigma_\square^i(f) = H_\square^i(f) F(f)$$

Response Input

i : node number
 σ_\square : $\sigma_{xx}, \sigma_{yy}, \sigma_{zz}, \tau_{xy}, \tau_{yz}, \tau_{zx}$

- Broad-band loadings in three direction
 - Distributed over wide range of frequencies

$$\text{Loading } \mathbf{G} = \begin{bmatrix} F_x(f) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & F_y(f) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & F_z(f) \end{bmatrix}$$

F_x, F_y, F_z : vibration in x, y, z -directions
 f : frequency

- Single vector containing six stress FRFs (for each direction)

$$\mathbf{H}^i(f) = [H_{\sigma_{xx}}^i(f) \quad H_{\sigma_{yy}}^i(f) \quad H_{\sigma_{zz}}^i(f) \quad H_{\tau_{xy}}^i(f) \quad H_{\tau_{yz}}^i(f) \quad H_{\tau_{xz}}^i(f)]^T \quad i = 1,2,3 \text{ (for } x, y, z)$$

- Single **response** calculation

- Representative response: Von Mises stress

$$G_{\text{mises}}(f) = \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^3 (\mathbf{H}^j)^* \mathbf{A} \mathbf{H}^i G_{ij}$$

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -0.5 & -0.5 \\ -0.5 & 1 & -0.5 \\ -0.5 & -0.5 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

\mathbf{H}^* : complex conjugate

T. Dirlik and D. Benasciutti, "Dirlik and Tovo-Benasciutti Spectral Methods in Vibration Fatigue: A Review with a Historical Perspective", *Metals* **2021**, 11(9), 2021.

G.M. Teixeira et al., "Random Vibration Fatigue: Frequency Domain Critical Plane Approaches", ASME, IMECE2013-62607, 2013.

- Dirlik's method

- calculates the probability of the occurrence of a certain amplitude in unit time

- **Probability density $p(S)$** of the occurrence of an amplitude of S is

$$p(S) = \left(\frac{c_1}{\tau} e^{-\frac{z}{\tau}} + \frac{c_2 z}{\alpha^2} e^{-\frac{z^2}{2\alpha^2}} + c_3 z e^{-\frac{z^2}{2}} \right) / (2\sqrt{m_0})$$

$$z = \frac{S}{2\sqrt{m_0}} \quad m_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^\infty f^n G_{mises}(f) df$$

$$x_m = \frac{m_1 \sqrt{m_2}}{m_0 \sqrt{m_4}} \quad \gamma = \frac{m_2}{\sqrt{m_0 m_4}} \quad c_1 = \frac{2(x_m - \gamma^2)}{1 + \gamma^2} \quad c_2 = \frac{1 - \gamma - c_1 + c_1^2}{1 - \alpha}$$

$$\alpha = \frac{\gamma - x_m - c_1^2}{1 - \gamma - c_1 + c_1^2} \quad \tau = \frac{1.25(\gamma - c_3 - c_2\alpha)}{c_1} \quad c_3 = 1 - c_1 - c_2$$

- Palmgren-Miner Rule

- Vibration linearly accumulates damage on the structure
- Failure criterion: Fails at damage $D \geq 1$

- Damage when applied n loading cycles (fixed amplitude):

$$D = \frac{n}{N}$$

n : number of applied loading cycles
 N : fatigue life at this load level (amplitude)

- Damage under variable amplitude load:

$$D = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{n(S_i)}{N(S_i)}$$

k : number of the different amplitudes
 S_i : amplitudes of load
 $n(S_i)$: number of cycles of amplitude S_i
 $N(S_i)$: fatigue life for amplitude S_i

- Damage under load according to $p(S)$:

$$D = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\mu p(S)}{N(S)} dS$$

$p(S)$: probability of amplitude S
 μ : number of peaks per unit time,
 $\mu = \sqrt{m_4} / \sqrt{m_2}$

→ Accumulated damage per unit time

Material Properties and Applied Loadings

- Mechanical properties and fatigue properties**

	Al [1]	LFT*	WFT*
E_{11} , GPa	68.9	5.49	14.30
E_{22} , GPa			11.47
ν_{12}	0.33	0.3	0.3
G_{12} , GPa	25.9	2.11	6.09

* Measured

Aluminum S-N curve [2]

Composite S-N curve [3]

- Applied random vibration (PSD form)**

– Loading time: 21 hours

Freq. (Hz)	X-dir. (g^2/Hz)	Y-dir. (g^2/Hz)	Z-dir. (g^2/Hz)
5	0.0125	0.04	0.05
10	0.03	0.04	0.06
20	0.03	0.04	0.06
200	0.00025	0.0008	0.0008

Standard: GB/T 31467.3

Unit $g = 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$

Applied random vibration

[1] ASM Matweb, "Aluminum 6061-T6; 6061-T651", <http://asm.matweb.com/search/SpecificMaterial.asp?bassnum=MA6061T6>, Retrieved in 2020-04-17.

[2] Yahr, G. T. "Fatigue Design Curves for 6061-T6 Aluminum", United States, doi:10.1115/1.2842286, <https://www.osti.gov/servlets/purl/10157028>, 1993.

[3] Bureau, M. N. and Denault, J. "Fatigue Resistance of Continuous Glass Fiber/Polypropylene Composites: Consolidation Dependence", *Composite Science and Technology*, 64, 2004

Boundary Conditions and Intermediate Results

Frequency Analysis

- Boundary conditions
 - Fix lower faces of external frame ($U_x=U_y=U_z=0$)

- Results: Total 20 natural modes

Harmonic Response Analysis

- Boundary Conditions and applied loadings

	X-dir.	Y-dir.	Z-dir.
Loading	Amplitude = 1g (9.81m/s ²) Frequency range: 0.1 Hz ~ 200 Hz		
Location	Lower faces of frame		
Constraint	U _x =free U _y =U _z =0	U _y =free U _x =U _z =0	U _z =free U _x =U _y =0

- Results : FRFs for 6 stress components

Results – Accumulated Fatigue Damage

- **21 hours** of random vibration
 - Standard: GB/T 31476.3
- No damage appeared in composite
- Weak regions appeared in Al frames
 - Due to heavy batteries

Weak region at the connections

Local weak regions

Results – Fatigue Damage on Al Frame

Results – Al+Composite vs. Full Al

- With same thickness, 12% weight reduction
- Similar locations of weak region (frame-plate connection)
- Only local reinforcement at the concentration point was needed

- **Mode-based numerical fatigue analysis on multi-material battery pack structure**
 - **Evaluation stage: Harmonic response of the structure**
 - Frequency analysis: eigenmodes and natural frequencies
 - Harmonic response analysis: frequency response functions
 - **Fatigue analysis stage: Fatigue analysis using random vibration**
 - Variable stress amplitude corresponding to random vibration
 - Fatigue life based on accumulation of fatigue damage
- **Fatigue analysis results**
 - **Regions to be reinforced and to be reduced could be identified**
 - Cover and carrier appeared to be safe from fatigue failure
 - Connection of frames and batteries were weak points
- **Future works**
 - **Fatigue properties dependent to composite direction**
 - **Fatigue failure criteria according to anisotropic stress**

Thank you